

Broadcast Core Network (BCN): Paving the Future Path of DTT

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Abstract—Terrestrial broadcasting has been considered outdated for decades because of its lack of flexibility in embracing emerging use cases on the IP media delivery landscape. Recent standardization efforts have been a turning point, bringing broadcasting technologies to the most efficient communication systems group and incorporating an IP-based protocol stack. However, a key enabler for integrating terrestrial broadcast systems as one of the IP multimedia multicast delivery choices is still missing: the development of a Broadcasting Core Network (BCN). This entity will entail innovative and more efficient management of the frequency resources assigned to the Broadcast Network Operator, maximize the capabilities of IP-based solutions, and eventually facilitate cooperation with other systems and the exposure of the broadcasting asset to additional services. In this paper, we build on the latest DTT standards to explain how the 5G Core developments drive the first steps of the standardization of a BCN. The paper also identifies the additional challenges that the broadcasting industry will face shortly to integrate the envisioned services, and it ends with the description of a prototype developed to furnish BCN standardization.

I. INTRODUCTION

BROADCAST networks have undergone two major technical revolutions since the dawn of the service in the early XXth century. The first was the switch from analog to digital television in the nineties. In contrast, the second currently targets integrating Internet Protocol (IP) technologies into the protocol stack, opening the door to transforming broadcast networks into more flexible multimedia and Information Technology (IT) infrastructures. The transition from analog to digital services mainly concentrated on incorporating the developments in physical layer and media compression techniques to the traditional broadcasting scheme: channel coding algorithms, efficient constellation design, new modulation schemes, video compression techniques, and many others. On the other hand, the second wave of reforms is currently targeting the broadcasting architecture, shaping its workflow to make it compatible with communication systems with IP as a core value. This evolution is assisting the broadcast industry to be a part of a contemporary media distribution solution, contending with Over The Top (OTT) platforms and exposing their services to non-broadcast networks and consumer devices [1].

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In 2013, the Advanced Television Systems Committee (ATSC) started the specifications of the last digital terrestrial television standard ATSC 3.0. It was the first non-3GPP Digital Terrestrial Television (DTT) to include a protocol stack pivoting on IP to facilitate the delivery of IP media and other multimedia internet content. IP also paves the floor to further advanced services using over-the-air broadcast signals. These potentials require new network architectures to provide flexibility to production, distribution, and transmission processes and infrastructures. This network architecture is based on creating a new Broadcast Core Network (BCN). Three ATSC Technical Groups (TG) are currently working on that objective (TG3/S43, the Implementation Team (IT)-5, and the TG3-11 [2], [3]). TG3/S43 seeks the addition of core networking capabilities as an integral part of the ATSC 3.0 network architecture. IT-5 is working on designing, implementing, and testing an Inter-Tower Communications Network (ITCN) and In-band Distribution Link (IDL) cases within an ATSC ecosystem [4], [5]. The Broadcast Core Network (BCN) defined in TG3/S43 will be agnostic to the physical layer, and consequently, it shall be compatible with other standards across the globe. Finally, TG3-11 is tasked to study and document how mobile network operators and the 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) could potentially leverage ATSC 3.0 as part of the 3GPP 5G System (5GS). The outcome is a set of scenarios and technologies that would enable the complementary use of 3GPP Multimedia Broadcast/Multicast Services (MBMS) and ATSC 3.0, the 5GS umbrella.

In Europe, the latest terrestrial delivery standard, Digital Video Broadcasting – Terrestrial 2 (DVB-T2) (2010), focused on optimizing the physical layer, and it was not developed targeting IP delivery. However, Digital Video Broadcasting (DVB) is currently developing a set of complementary standards and amendments to its existing portfolio to facilitate a full IP environment that addresses consumer and professional applications for DVB broadcast bearers. This initiative is referred to as DVB-NIP (Native IP DVB). Under the DVB-NIP umbrella, DVB-I provides service discovery, program metadata, and infrastructure to access DVB content from non-DVB networks (Wireless Local Area Network (WLAN), 4th Generation (4G), 5th Generation (5G)). DVB-AVC (Audio Video Coding) and DVB-DASH (Dynamic Adaptive Streaming over HTTP) for source coding and stream formatting. Finally, DVB-MABR (Multicast Adaptive Bitrate), DVB-GSE (Generic Stream Encapsulation), and the physical layer (PHY) specifications DVB-S2 (Satellite 2), DVB-S2X (extension of

DVB-S2), and DVB-T2 deal with the transport.

In other regions, a similar trend is observed. The Japanese Advanced Integrated Services Digital Broadcasting - Terrestrial (ISDB-T) proposes MPEG Media Transport (MMT) and Type-Length-Value (TLV) for content transport. MMT is based on IP, so this standard can also provide services that combine broadcasting and other communication systems using IP packets [6]. More recently, the Call for Proposals for the "TV 3.0 Project" run by the Brazilian Digital Terrestrial Television System (SBTVD-T) described the prerequisite of an IP-based transport Layer. Indeed, the results published later in [7] as part of the study led to the decision to recommend adopting Real-time Object Delivery over Unidirectional Transport/Dynamic Adaptive Streaming over HTTP (ROUTE/DASH). In China, while the proposed Digital Terrestrial Multimedia Broadcast (DTMB-A) focuses on the PHY, one of the largest cellular operators (China Broadcasting Network) has proposed a core network applicable to China radio and television for the rapid deployment of 5G broadcasting services [8].

Eventually, it should be noted that two reports are under development at the Radiocommunication Sector of the International Telecommunication Union - Radiocommunication Sector (ITU-R) Working Party (WP) 6B. They target the BCN fundamentals for digital television and the technological enablers of an ITCN network.

After analyzing the different research and standardization development efforts in previous lines, it is clear that IP-based approaches are becoming predominant in the broadcasting ecosystem. However, a BCN standardization is still missing to bridge the gap between the current transmitter infrastructure (Radio Access Network, RAN), the rest of the production and distribution assets, as well as with services at the application layer. This entity, concurrently with all other solutions described before, would further integrate the broadcasting facilities into the IP media delivery landscape. Among other things, it will enable an easy convergence with other systems and promote new use cases that will be the new revenue generators the broadcasting industry seeks.

This paper presents a 5G Core (5GC)-based BCN architectural proposal in Section II, and then the challenges associated with the newly envisioned use cases are detailed in Section III. Then, Section IV presents a DEMO prototyping of a realistic implementation, and finally, Section V describes the expected path and possible timeline toward an international standard describing a BCN.

II. BCN ARCHITECTURE PROPOSAL: LESSONS LEARNED FROM 5GC

A. Legacy DTT Architecture

The ITU handbook on DTT describes a system architecture based on a downlink-only, one-to-many media transmission path that has prevailed based on the same paradigm with little variations up to our days. The classical architecture of any DTT standard transmission part can be divided into four subsystems (Broadcast Center, Transport, RAN, and Reception/Display), as represented at the top of Fig. 1.

Content creation is carried out (or assembled) at the Broadcast Center, where raw video compression and application-level error protection are completed. The Service Multiplex (MUX) and Transport, assembles the digital data stream into information packets with univocal identification and eventually multiplexes the video, audio, and ancillary data into a single stream. Then, the transport subsystem routes this resultant stream to each RAN tower. The Radio Frequency (RF) transmission stage transforms the channel-coded digital data stream information into a modulated signal ready for broadcasting. Finally, DTT receivers tune, process, and display the content.

However, even after the significant evolution of the physical layer (Low-Density Parity-Check (LDPC), Non-Uniform Quadrature Amplitude Modulation (NU-QAM), Layer Division Multiplexing (LDM), Combined Interleaving) in the RF Transmission Center side, transport (e.g., ROUTE, MMT) in the Broadcast Center side, and link layer protocols development (e.g., ATSC Link-Layer Protocol (ALP), GSE), the data distribution architecture has not undertaken any substantial changes. Consequently, the main blocks described in Fig. 1 (top row) can still be easily identified in any widely spread DTT standard (1st and second-generation systems, namely DVB-T, DVB-T2, ATSC 1.0, ATSC 3.0, DTMB-A, or ISDB-T). So, even if the latest DTT standards are among the most spectrally efficient systems, their rigid network architecture refrains them from being part of the current use case and services.

B. 5GC Architecture

3GPP Release 15 (Rel-15) described the 5G Service-Based Architecture (SBA) for the first time. A set of specifications drove this approach. First, *modularity* should support various communication scenarios and pose different network needs as the authors describe in [9]. Modularity turned out to be one of the critical drivers of the network slicing concept, a 5G flagship. Secondly, *openness* should support new services exposing network capabilities to broadcast operator's services and third-party applications. Third, *extensibility* will facilitate the interaction between different services and should remain guaranteed without introducing a new reference point and the corresponding message flows. Lastly, it should support separate Control and User planes, allowing for independent evolution of core network and RANs through Network Function Virtualization (NFV). NFV also contributes to improved scalability, flexibility, and cost-effective service provisioning [10], [11].

Following those requirements, the main difference between 5GC and previous network architectures was the usage of service-based interactions between Network Functions (NFs) instead of the traditional "nodes" or "network elements" connected by interfaces. Each NF offers one or more services to other NFs relying on the widely used "Hypertext Transfer Protocol (HTTP) Representational State Transfer (REST) paradigm" as a communication method. Fig. 1 (central row) contains a typical representation of a 5G SBA, including a selection of the main NFs and associated interfaces with the gNodeB (Radio Access Technology (RAT) for 5G).

Fig. 1. DTT and Mobile Legacy Architectures to propose BCN for Future DTT

Recently, Release 16 presented the enhanced Service Based Architecture (eSBA), which improved flexible deployments of Session Management Function (SMF) and User Plane Functions (UPF), added support for commercial services using location-based service architecture enabled RAN Self-Organizing Networks, and provided Dual Connectivity and Carrier Aggregation enhancements [11].

C. BCN system outline

The limitations of current ATSC network architectures (flexibility, modularity, amongst others) have been identified by relevant broadcast industry stakeholders. The current architectural design lacks flexibility and modularity to incorporate new services; the closeness and tightness of its workflow make it very hard to expose its functionalities to 3rd parties; and the lack of a superior management entity hinders its integration with other technologies, such as 5G. The ATSC already identified the architectural design during the standardization of ATSC 3.0 and is currently working on the technical details of a Broadcast Core Network as part of the ATSC 3.0 standard portfolio. Meanwhile, academia has also spent research efforts in the same direction [2], [3]. Up to now, challenges are similar to those that led to an SBA solution in 3GPP. Consequently, the preferred choice is a service-based Core Network (CN). Unfortunately, applying 5GC directly to the DTT ecosystem is not feasible for the current broadcast infrastructure and service peculiarities. First, the Free-to-Air (FTA) use case is the pivoting point of the whole system, and its relevance will remain for some years. The receiver should be able to decode the media signal without any Subscriber Identity Module (SIM) card or associated pre-paid service. In addition, there is

no direct support for an uplink channel, and IP connectivity cannot be taken for granted in all parts of the world. Lastly, the regulations of the infrastructures and the frequency planning are also different for the DTT systems.

Therefore, even if the overall architecture is the same and the general purpose of some NFs is similar, the particularities of the DTT networks require the definition of a specific BCN. The solution proposed in Fig. 1 (Bottom row) is taken from [3]. On the left side, it presents the SBA set of NFs, whose instances should be adapted to the requirements of DTT networks. Then, on the right side, the bcNode concept arises. This entity is an upgrade of a traditional broadcast facility that encompasses capabilities conceptually associated with a gNodeB. Likewise, a bsNode is included at the studio to interface between the production workflow and the BCN.

Nevertheless, updating the DTT network with its own architecture based on the Core Network concept will imply a series of challenges that need to be analyzed to detect use cases and propose new ones. The next section will describe the potential challenges to implementing some use cases in the updated SBA-based BCN DTT system.

III. REQUIREMENTS FOR DELIVERING NEW SERVICES

In [3], the authors compiled a comprehensive list of the most relevant use cases that will flourish under the development of a prospective BCN. They had the power to revolutionize the broadcast industry, leading to new ways to monetize the broadcast spectrum. On the one hand, a group of enhanced services would work seamlessly with legacy infrastructures and current linear services. On the other hand, another set of new applications will require further modifications in standards

TABLE I
ENABLED AND ENHANCED USE CASES AND CHALLENGES ASSOCIATED WITH THEM

USE CASES	CHALLENGES					Major/Minor	Ref.
	Return Channel	Low-Latency	Standardization	Self-Int. Canc.	Liaisons		
ITCN/IDL	-	-	X	X	-	Minor	[3], [4]
Opportunistic PLP	-	-	X	-	-	Minor	[12]
BNO/BVNO Management	-	-	X	-	X	Minor	[2]
Convergence	-	-	X	-	X	Major	[3]
Automotive	-	-	X	-	X	Major	[3]
Dynamic Radio Resource Allocation	X	-	X	-	X	Major	[13]
IoT	X	-	X	-	X	Major	[3]
Cloud Content Production	X	X	-	-	X	Major	[3]

and current infrastructures. In this section, the authors spotlight the additional challenges of BCN-enabled use cases. The problems are also classified as minor or major depending on the expected amount of modifications to overcome them.

First, the envisioned ITCN and IDL distribution and communication approaches described in [4] seek to double the spectrum efficiency of broadcasting infrastructures. The system's success relies on a self-interference cancellation algorithm to be included in the transmitter facility for full-duplex systems that is still to be developed. Lately, promising results have already been presented in [4], [5] to cancel the expected RF signal and receive the unknown RF signal from other DTT towers. So the transmission towers could communicate between them by using the single-frequency network (all of them using the same frequency) if they cancel the information already known (in-band). However, as long as this canceller is not deployed, the transmitters in the ITCN must use neighboring or adjacent frequencies. Second, the authors in [12] also explain how a BCN could enable a constant 100% usage of the available throughput on any RF channel, using the available space for delivering Hyper-Personalized Advertisements or Educational content. In this case, the main challenge relies on proposing new signaling fields within the ALP, which might require working with the standardization forum. Then, there is also the automatic and seamless management of a network broadcasting group presented in [2], which might require an update on some of the signaling procedures and an agreement between different parties. In this case, it is expected that the BCN will control, orchestrate, and synchronize the spectrum resources of different operators, allowing the existence of Broadcast Virtual Network Operators (BVNO). The future convergence scenario is another use case that will bring challenges covered in previous paragraphs: liaison agreements between parties and some standardization effort. After multiple works focused on the physical layer convergence, the BCN offers for the first time an opportunity for the broadcasters to cooperate with other networks (e.g., Satellite, Wireless Fidelity (WiFi), 3GPP) as peers. Finally, the BCN could also enable a spectrum-efficient map software or firmware upgrade for automotive service if the previously described shortcomings are addressed.

On the other hand, there are also more demanding use cases that require to fulfill one of the aspirations of broadcaster networks for many years: the existence of a return channel. Nevertheless, this should not be interpreted as the classical

uplink channel of cellular User Equipment (UE) but as the complementary return link that a set-top box could offer through a WLAN connection or as the information conveyed from the upgraded transmission facilities (i.e., bcNodes) to the BCN. For instance, the Dynamic Radio Resource Allocation use case would entitle the BCN to handle the contents and their quality dynamically and share the spectrum as a service among different Broadcast Network Operators (BNOs) [13]. This approach will benefit from a return channel to measure the actual audience synchronized to a particular service and the statistics of each broadcasting facility. Then, in the case of the Internet of Things (IoT) service for rural areas, a return path, at least for the gateway, will be a requirement for a successful implementation. However, the connected cars using Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) communications to interchange their status information for making decisions in the autonomous driving service require an ultra-reliable and low latency response [14].

Eventually, the Remote Content Production described in [3] is also an option that draws the industry's attention to the BCN approach. The challenge here is twofold. First, a return path is required to enable contribution links for mobile units, and second, low-latency communications are required at the BCN part for the live media delivery. Table I presents a summary of the challenges related to each use case described in this section.

IV. PROTOTYPING THE FUTURE OF BROADCASTING

A. Envisioned Architecture

This section illustrates the previous concepts with a prototype built on existing legacy equipment and ad-hoc software (SW) modules that are compatible with current standards. The network prototype includes a basic BCN managing two upgraded ATSC 3.0 transmission facilities (bcNodes) sharing an ITCN communication channel. The architecture block diagram is depicted in upper Fig. 2.

The BCN follows the SBA of Section II and gathers a minimum set of NFs that communicate with each other through HTTP REST. The NF's instances are accessed through an Application Program Interfaces (API) as defined in [3]. The essential NFs included in this version of the BCN are the Coordinator Network Function (CNF) or the orchestrator, which acts as the interface between the BCN and the bcNode and the User Interface Function (UIF). The latter is a management module in charge of selecting the operating mode of the transmitter and the correspondent configuration

Fig. 2. Envisioned architecture for a DTT network containing a BCN.

parameters. Other NF modules in the BCN are the Network Repository Function (NRF) and the Authentication Network Function (AUNF), which have identical functionality to the 5GC, but have been downscaled to accommodate the needs of the simpler BCN.

The bottom part of Fig. 2 describes the transmitter signal configuration. The first transmitter (Wilmington), using a bcNode, has a Studio to Transmitter Link (STL) from the Broadcaster production/distribution facilities (Broadcast Center). In this Proof-of-Concept (PoC), the Broadcast Center is a software service representing the studio in charge of reading the contents and sending them over one User Datagram Protocol over IP (UDP/IP) socket per stream. Transmitter one (Tx-1) radiates the content to the designated coverage area at 725 MHz. The Tx-1 footprint has a DTT receiver (DTT Rx 1). A second transmitter (Jacksonville) also uses a bcNode. As shown in Fig. 2, Jacksonville’s transmitter (Tx-2) does not have an STL link to the Broadcasting center and uses the content conveyed by Tx 1 as the contribution link. Embedding the contribution content within the broadcasted signal is a particular application of the ITCN network use case described before. Finally, there will be another two receivers in the Jacksonville coverage area (DTT Rx 2 and DTT Rx 3). Both transmitters will also have access to a Content Delivery Network (CDN), a server that stores the available contents for the transmitter.

Finally, the three receivers fit into two different groups. On the one hand, Rx 1 and Rx 2 are commercial Set-Top Boxes (STBs) from LowaSYS that can decode the legacy ATSC 3.0 content. On the other hand, Rx 3 is a modified DTA-2131 DekTec card receiver that can access and decode the new datacasting service presented later on. The main reason for using a different receiver is that RX 3 required decoding a group of signaling fields at the ALP protocol that were not mandatory, which the commercial LowaSYS receivers did not implement.

B. Use Cases and Prototyping

The BCN is the system manager in charge of controlling the two regional transmitters depicted in Fig. 2. Even if it has enhanced capacities, the first transmitter operates as a legacy ATSC 3.0 transmitter, which has an STL connection with the Broadcasting Center and conveys two multiplexed services using LDM. The Core Layer (CL) and the Enhance Layer (EL) deliver legacy media streams with a bandwidth of 5.12 Mbps and 10.8 Mbps, respectively. EL conveys a delayed version of the uplink stream with a different resolution as a contribution link for an ITCN network. Both PHY configurations offer a bandwidth close to the requirements of the media streams. It must be noted that it is nearly impossible to match the numbers exactly; thus, there are always some unused bits per second in the stream. As shown in Fig. 2, Tx-1 uses null packets in both layers, while Tx-2 uses a no-sensitive video stream to fulfill these spaces.

In Mode 0, the broadcaster specifies that the second transmitter needs to ingest its contribution from an ITCN network and that available space should be filled with an HyperPersonalized advertisement targeting Rx 3. In the advertisement time, Rx 3 will pop up the HyperPersonalized advertisement data-casted by Tx-2 (using the Opportunistic PLP use case). The bcNode in Tx-2 is also in charge of synchronizing the different media flows, so commercial receivers within the footprints of Tx-1 and Tx-2 receive aligned content. In a timeline overview, the Rx 1 and Rx 2 decode and show the same content during the regular time and add time. Rx 3 only decodes (not shown) these videos because it displays a console with text messages. It decodes and shows the HyperPersonalized advertisement inserted using the Opportunistic PLP use case.

In Mode 1, the previous services are maintained, but one of the critical business cases for the operator is also included: target advertisement. The only change is that, during the advertisement timeslot, the Jacksonville transmitter does not use video No. 2 (*Jewel in Palace* in Table II) received from the air. In contrast, it accesses content from the CDN and broadcasts video No. 3 (*Korean discovery* in Table II), which

TABLE II
DIFFERENT MEDIA REPRESENTATION MAIN CHARACTERISTICS.

No.	Title	Content	Tx	Format	RT	Rate	Mode 0	Mode 1	Mode 2
1	Big Buck Bunny (ITCN)	Live	1, 2	ALP	Yes	4.5 Mbps	X	X	
2	Jewel in Palace	Ad: Nation-Wide	1	ALP	Yes	5.5 Mbps	X		
3	Korean discovery	Ad: Regional	2	ALP	Yes	8.7 Mbps		X	
4	Bilbao promo	Ad: HyPersonalized	2	MP4	No	15.5 Mbps	X	X	
5	Crash Landing on You	Alarm	1, 2	ALP	Yes	2.2 Mbps			X

lasts 30 seconds. So, Rx 2 would show the *Korean discovery* program while Rx 1 would show *Jewel in Palace* (see Table II).

Eventually, a *Mode 2* is related to the Emergency Alert System (EAS). In this case, the broadcaster has received an alert from a nationwide mechanism, and the system can seamlessly change to this mode. Therefore, both transmitters stop the ongoing broadcast transmissions, access the pre-recorded alarm, and instantly put it on the air so that all receivers will play video No. 5 synchronously. This architecture could also reconfigure the PHY parameters to guarantee the physical robustness of the signal. Another advantage of this mode is that if the broadband network is down, the second transmitter could directly take the alarm media from transmitter one with an ITCN.

V. WHEN WILL WE SEE THE BCN IN THE FIELD?

Defining a BCN is currently addressed in ATSC 3.0 TG3/S43 specialist group. According to its schedule, the technical proposals received by this working group will be evaluated by 2023. It is then expected that by late 2023, the group will be actively working on the standardization process. Meanwhile, the academic work started in 2020 will likely grow steadily over this opportunity window. The solutions to the challenges described in Table I and the requirements for the technology's Verification & Validation (V&V) process are not trivial and will involve significant research and development effort.

In parallel, the technical group ATSC IT-5 is building a technology demonstrator of the ITCN technology. This Proof-of-Concept will be deployed in the field test facilities that Humber College is preparing near the Toronto area. The work presented in Section IV is one of the candidate test cases on the field trials covering these technologies by 2023. Likewise, ITU WP-6B will keep on with its study reports focused on BCN and ITCN technologies until the end of 2023.

The DVB working plan, updated in July 2022, does not foresee the definition of a BCN. Nevertheless, it includes, among other things, the V&V process of DVB-NIP and the definition of the DVB-I integration over the 5G infrastructure, which will define the procedure and sequence of interactions between the DVB-DASH client/server and the 5G enhanced MBMS (eMBMS) client/server.

Eventually, the 3GPP standardization group has approved a Work Item (WI) DTTB4MBS, which aims to allow "the usage of non-3GPP Digital Terrestrial Broadcast networks for multicast/broadcast services in 5GS through interworking of non-3GPP DTT with 5GS". This DTTB4MBS report is well aligned with TS22.261, where the 5GS support for multi-cast/broadcast services is analyzed to reduce the congestion

in cellular networks. This work will probably be part of the Release 19 standardization efforts.

VI. CONCLUSION

The current network architecture of broadcast facilities presents fundamental barriers (flexibility, modularity, and interfacing, among others) to be part of the future 5G/6G wireless network infrastructure. This paper has described the capital importance of integrating a BCN into the classical broadcast architecture to maintain the competitiveness of this point-to-multipoint media delivery industry. The BCN will be inspired by the developments of 3GPP 5GC, but it will require attention to the specific requirements of DTT networks.

The authors deployed an ITCN prototype built on legacy equipment and ad-hoc software modules compatible with current DTT standards (ATSC 3.0). The prototype does not require a signal cancellation because the network uses different frequencies to broadcast the signal. However, it was relevant to validate that the communication protocol between the towers successfully detected the new fields for sending ITCN information without receiver affection. Moreover, using the Opportunistic PLP to send Hyper-Personalized Advertisements to the users, the authors demonstrate the viability of a flexible and scalable system for inserting any content for future services. In addition, with Mode 2, it was possible to detect and synchronize all the equipment to notify emergencies, even if the secondary transmitter was not connected to the STL.

In short, this is a hectic time for the broadcasting industry, and research communities, where different Standards Developing Organizations (SDOs), research institutes, and academia are working directly or with concepts close to the BCN, a fundamental tool to incorporate innovative services over DTT infrastructure in the following years.

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